

Artificial intelligence in language education: Teachers' fears, hopes and solutions

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Abstract

The potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to improve educational outcomes, especially in language learning, has been widely discussed. Yet, the lived realities, expectations, and concerns educators have about AI's role in schools remain unexplored. This commentary looks at a comparative study involving 636 second language teachers from Brazil, Finland, Hong Kong, and South Korea. It examines how educators perceive and use AI. The results show generally positive attitudes but highlight differences in self-efficacy, usage frequency, and pedagogical value. These differences are shaped by regional policies and digital resources. Understanding these insights is important for guiding teacher training, policy design, and the development of ethical, inclusive tools that respond to local needs.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Teacher Training; Second Language Teachers; Comparative Study.*

JEL Classification: I21; I23; O33.

1. Listening to teachers: Why context matters

Language education is a very human activity that demands responsiveness, cultural sensitivity and adaptability to meet the needs of diverse learners. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies offer to facilitate this work through features such as automated feedback, personalised content, and immersive environments (Kong et al., 2024a; Wang et al., 2025). However, teachers are not passive consumers of new technologies but active mediators whose beliefs, confidence, and pedagogical values shape whether and how such technologies are integrated into practice. Across diverse educational settings, teachers' engagement with AI has been found to be influenced by a variety of factors, including digital competence, pedagogical beliefs, institutional backing, perceived usefulness and ease of use of the AI technology, and ethical concerns associated with AI technology use (Talha et al., 2025). In Brazil, higher education institutions are beginning to explore the use of generative AI, however, integration remains uneven needing more policy and faculty development support (de la Torre & Baldeon-Calisto, 2024). In Finland, teacher educators perceive both opportunities and risks, viewing AI rather as a tool for personalisation and support, at the same time being also concerned about the implications for human-centred pedagogy and professional teacher autonomy (Vartiainen et al., 2024). In Hong Kong, teachers' intentions to adopt AI are shaped by perceived usefulness, self-efficacy, and ethical concerns (Kong et al., 2024b). In South Korea, the adoption of AI is driven by motivation, ease of use, and social factors, with research indicating that frequent users of such applications as ChatGPT are more likely to promote their use among peers, indicating normalisation across academic and professional environments (Jo, 2023a, 2023b). In all these diverse contexts, there is a clear indication that the adoption of AI is never just a matter of technical availability. Rather, it depends on supportive policies, teachers' pedagogical orientations, perceptions of usefulness and self-efficacy, and the influence of professional and social

networks. Emphasising these shared dynamics helps situate the present commentary within the wider cross-cultural dialogue on AI in education.

In 2024, we conducted a comparative survey among 636 second language teachers in Brazil (n = 133), Finland (n = 174), Hong Kong (n = 133), and South Korea (n = 196), complemented with an open commentary section. Teachers were selected through voluntary participation online and offline, with inclusion criteria requiring prior teaching experience. Recently qualified teachers without classroom experience were not included. Regarding teaching experience, 64.5% of the respondents had 1–10 years of experience, 24.2% had 11–20 years, 7.0% had 21–30 years, and 4.3% had more than 31 years of experience. The study found that attitudes towards AI were generally positive across all four regions. Nevertheless, significant differences among regions emerged in terms of AI self-efficacy, usage frequency, and perceived pedagogical value. These differences were not random; they were based on the digital infrastructure, policy environment, teacher education systems, and cultural orientations towards technology and pedagogy in each region. In what follows, we focus on these differences to illustrate how teachers' beliefs and professional contexts shape the adoption and pedagogical use of AI.

2. Four regions and four perspectives

South Korean educators exhibited a higher level of confidence in AI utilisation than their counterparts in other regions. The nation-imposed priority of innovation based on AI and serious internet infrastructure also backs up South Korea's competence and the use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) (The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2021). Still, this confidence did not necessarily mean that teachers had high expectations about the teaching potential of AI. Teachers were optimistic about the potential of AI regarding real-time feedback and efficiency but were less convinced about its capacity to perform more complex tasks, such as personalisation and immersive learning. This indicates that technical confidence does not automatically equate to pedagogical trust.

Teachers in Hong Kong showed the opposite pattern: moderate levels of self-efficacy but very high expectations for the impact of AI. These teachers were particularly positive about the potential of AI to assist in assessment and targeted interventions, which could reflect the performance-oriented education system in this region and strong institutional emphasis on digital innovation. However, our findings also suggest that these expectations may be driven more by top-down policy promotion than by classroom experience.

Finnish teachers approached AI with reflective caution. Despite their low self-efficacy scores, these teachers exhibited high interest in AI and had clear expectations for how it might support feedback, inclusive teaching, and learner autonomy. Consistent with the pedagogical culture of Finland, Finnish teachers seemed to evaluate AI tools based on ethical fit and instructional alignment and not on novelty or speed. They demonstrated a strong emphasis on human-centred pedagogy and critical digital literacy.

Teachers in Brazil were both enthusiastic and ambivalent. They reported having a high interest in immersive and gamified applications, suggesting that they desired to engage learners in motivating, tech-enhanced environments. At the same time, discomfort among teachers in Brazil was more common than in other regions, likely reflecting uneven access to educational technologies, limited institutional support, and concerns about ethical or cultural mismatches. Brazilian teachers appeared eager but undersupported, as they navigated a complex mix of aspiration and uncertainty.

3. Beyond attitudes: What shapes AI acceptance?

Although all four contexts revealed a baseline level of openness to AI, actual AI readiness and usage varied widely. We identified three main factors that seem to drive language teachers' acceptance of using AI tools in their teaching and learning activities:

AI self-efficacy: Teachers' belief in their ability to use AI tools effectively was a major factor in their expectations of the usefulness of these tools in their classrooms. This supports Bandura's (1986) well-established concept of self-efficacy and aligns with the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003), which identifies effort and performance expectancy as central predictors of technology adoption. This study ultimately found that confidence alone is not enough for AI use in classrooms, as it must be accompanied by pedagogical evidence to ensure effective implementation.

Pedagogical orientation: Teachers not only asked "Can I use AI?" but increasingly "Is AI worth using?" Their responses revealed strong value judgements. Furthermore, for example, Finnish and Brazilian teachers emphasised inclusion and personalisation, while Hong Kong teachers focused on assessment efficiency. These orientations influenced how these teachers interpreted the usefulness of AI, and teachers' educational philosophies really shaped how they viewed AI's potential in their specific contexts.

Institutional and policy context: Teachers' expectations were shaped by their environments. In Hong Kong, strong policy signals and digital infrastructure raised expectations, even among teachers with lower levels of confidence in AI. In Brazil, teachers' uneven access to educational technology and limited policy coherence targeting AI use in classrooms created uncertainty. Our study shows that, across the board, systemic conditions—policy support, infrastructure, training—either amplify or dampen teachers' willingness to adopt AI. This echoes UNESCO's (2023, 2024) call for AI strategies that are ethical, inclusive, and context-responsive, particularly in education systems seeking to close digital divides and foster sustainable innovation.

Implications for practice and policy: Our findings suggest that promoting AI adoption in education requires more than just technical solutions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Strategies for effective AI integration in education

Note: Author's own elaboration based on the study findings.

Implementing strategies for meaningful and effective AI integration in education (Figure 1) must begin with listening to teachers and engaging them in ethical, context-sensitive dialogue. National-level strategies should invest not only in upgrading technology but also in teachers' professional development and in ensuring that they have hands-on experience with AI tools and feel confident using them in real classrooms. Grounding innovation in the realities of educational practice ensures that system development responds to actual needs, making technical investments both purposeful and sustainable. In other words, real-world teaching conditions must inform every step forward. The implications of the study for practice and policy are as follows:

For teacher education and professional development: Not only must training address technical skill but also ought to explore how teaching methods adapt to AI. Reflective dialogue around ethics, inclusion, and teacher agency is crucial,

especially in culturally diverse or under-resourced settings. Teachers need hands-on experience with AI tools embedded in collaborative and supportive peer-environments to build both confidence in and critical awareness of AI use in education.

For policymakers and system leaders: National strategies should include context-sensitive guidelines rather than one-size-fits-all expectations. Investment in infrastructure must be paired with trust-building efforts, transparency, and respect for teachers' professional judgments. Policies should avoid technosolutionism and frame AI as a support tool within a broader pedagogical vision.

For developers and edtech companies: Teachers should be engaged at an early stage and often during the design process to ensure cultural and instructional alignment. Features that support feedback, inclusivity, as well as autonomy should be prioritised, rather than gimmicks or productivity metrics alone. Finally, teachers' concerns about how AI could result in bias, data privacy, and student overreliance on technology should be clearly and proactively addressed.

4. Concluding thoughts: Centring teachers in the future of AI

AI in education is not just a question of innovation but also of values. As our study conducted across four regions shows, teachers approach AI through the lenses of their pedagogical beliefs, cultural contexts, and lived experiences. Thus, their insights should not be an afterthought in AI development; they should be a starting point. If we want AI to support equity, inclusion, and meaningful learning, we must focus on the people who make education happen every day: the teachers. This involves not only equipping them with the necessary AI tools, but also listening to their hopes, fears, and wisdom as we build the digital classrooms of tomorrow.

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